

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17008997

Management Of Nigerian Education For Economic Recovery: Challenges And Prospects

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Abstract

This paper examines the management of education in Nigeria as a tool for sustainable economic development. Historically, Nigeria's educational reforms, including the National Policy on Education, sought inclusivity, decentralization, and quality assurance, but implementation has been undermined by political instability, inadequate funding, and corruption. Current challenges include chronic underfunding, resource mismanagement, skill mismatches, high unemployment, brain drain, and poor digital access, all of which limit the sector's capacity to support national growth. The paper argues that aligning educational outcomes with labor market demands, especially in digital literacy and critical thinking, is crucial to bridging skill gaps and reducing unemployment. Furthermore, innovative management strategies such as integrating technology education, strengthening teacher training, investing in infrastructure, and fostering public-private partnerships can reposition education as a driver of recovery. Stakeholder engagement, from communities to industry, is emphasized as critical for accountability and relevance. By prioritizing accessibility, quality, and relevance, Nigeria can harness education to stimulate innovation, entrepreneurship, and long-term economic resilience. The study concludes that effective educational management is indispensable to addressing unemployment, curbing brain drain, and ensuring sustainable national development.

Keywords: Education management, economic recovery, skill gap, human capital

INTRODUCTION

The dynamic nature of current social, economic and political challenges Nigeria is entangled with has precipitated unprecedented disruptions to her economy, necessitating a need to revive it. It is this need that has led to a reevaluation of management of educational as a pivotal component of economic recovery. According to Ojerinde, (2011) the interdependence between education and economic stability is evidence that education serves not only as a catalyst for individual career development but also as a foundational element for societal advancement. Education is a cornerstone of economic development, influencing labor market outcomes, productivity, and innovation.

A well-managed education system equips individuals with the necessary skills to thrive in an evolving economy, thus facilitating a robust recovery from economic downturns (Qiang, 2015). Olasehinde-Williams (2018) also postulates that the alignment of educational outcomes with labor market needs is

essential, as industries are increasingly demanding a workforce adept in digital literacy and critical thinking. It is for this reason the World Bank (2021) underscores that investments in education yield significant returns, particularly in times of economic distress, where skilled workforce can drive recovery initiatives and adapt to new economic realities.

In accord with the above assertions, Nwafor et al. (2015) avers that education is integral to fostering human capital, which is essential for economic growth and a well-educated workforce is more adaptable, innovative, and capable of driving productivity. During times of economic downturn, investments in education can yield significant returns, as it equips individuals with the skills necessary to meet the demands of a changing labor market. Furthermore, Ajayi, (2017) proposes education can stimulate economic activity by increasing consumer spending and reducing unemployment rates. Thus, the management of educational systems during recovery phases is critical, necessitating a focus on accessibility, quality, and relevance of education.

In the light of these create benefits of education as a tool for economic development, relating same to the Nigerian environment, the state of Nigeria's educational system has not significantly improved the country's economy as there is high presence of skill gap between what the education system is producing for the economy and what is actually needed to drive the economy. This is evidenced in the education system's inability to produce required skilled and relevant productive graduates, hence the nation is still import dependent and a consumer nation. This has hindered Nigeria's economic growth and development due to the prevalence of leakages in the economy

Closely following the issue of skill gap is the unemployment level Edesiri (2021), avers that the lack of employable skills among graduates contributes to high unemployment rates. This is on the premise that most of the courses offered in schools are counter productive and not related to the immediate needs for economic development of Nigeria hence most of these graduates are unemployable as they lack required skill. This has led to social unrest, cybercrime and other vices that has increased economic instability.

On issues of brain drain which is a more recent challenge to the Nigerian economy, the perceived low quality of domestic educational system has made many talented Nigerian students to seek education abroad. This issue of brain drain has led to a loss of talent and skills that could help to boost economic recovery collectively.

A Brief Historical Context of Educational Management in Nigeria

The evolution of educational management in Nigeria can be traced back to the colonial era, where education was primarily aimed at producing clerks and laborers to serve the colonial administration. Post-independence, the focus shifted towards creating a more inclusive and functional educational system that caters to the diverse needs of the Nigerian populace. The introduction of various educational reforms, including the National Policy on Education (NPE) in 1977 and its subsequent revisions, aimed to address the challenges faced by the sector. These reforms have emphasized the need for decentralized management, community participation, and quality assurance in educational institutions. However, the implementation of these policies has been inconsistent, often hampered by political instability, inadequate funding, and infrastructural deficiencies.

Problems of Educational Management in Nigeria

Education is a pivotal factor in the development of any nation, serving as a foundation for economic growth, social cohesion, and the overall well-being of its populace. In Nigeria, the educational sector has undergone significant transformations since independence in 1960. However, the state of educational management in Nigeria remains fraught with challenges that impede its effectiveness and efficiency in the wake of the new normal of Nigeria characterized by high level of insecurity, hunger, poverty and unemployment.

First of its challenges is the issue of funding. Many educational institutions have experienced budget cuts, leading to larger class sizes, reduced staff, poor quality outputs and diminished resources (Ajayi, 2017). A major cause of this challenge is failure to the commitment of allocating 20% of the national budget to education as stated in the National Policy on Education 2013, which government flagrantly ignore and

refuse to abide by which makes actual allocations to education often fall short. Relatedly, Nwafor et al. (2015) affirms that with Nigerian governments operating under fiscal constraints, reallocating resources to education has been contentious as there is always a challenge between balancing immediate economic recovery needs with long-term investments in educational infrastructure. This financial strain has hindered the ability to provide quality education and support for the higher percentage of the vulnerable populations which exacerbates existing inequalities (Ishaya & Ogunode, 2021)

Poor funding is closely followed by issues of corruption and mismanagement. Corruption within the educational sector has led to the misallocation of resources, undermining the effectiveness of educational policies. Instances of embezzlement, bribery, and nepotism have created a culture of distrust among stakeholders in education, further complicating the management landscape (Edinoh et al., 2024). Ogunode and Paul (2021) postulates that the insufficient funds budgeted and released for employment of teachers are looted or diverted by some administrators in the educational institution and replace these employments by institutionalizing ghost workers protocol in their various schools thereby collecting their salaries instead of employing the teachers in the schools. In recent times, ghost workers corruption is one of the most common form of corruption in the educational institutions in Nigeria. For example, Premium Times (2020) published that in Kwara State, the state government has suspended a permanent secretary and four other senior officials over their alleged involvement in the recruitment of ‘fake’ teachers and suspicious deductions of workers’ salary at the State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB). The minister of finance and budget in Nigeria revealed that over 70,000 ghost workers that have been identified through the approved Integrated Payroll and Personnel Information System (IPPIS) (Ogunode&Paul2020; Naiare news 2020). Also, in Imo state, the Governor of Imo state Governor Hope Uzo dimm observed that the state has uncovered over 1,000 ghost workers, including more than 60 “dead or non-existent persons” in its schools.

Again, the rapid transition to online learning has highlighted significant disparities in digital access and literacy. Thus, technological advancements necessitate a reevaluation of curricula to ensure they are aligned with current and future labor market demands (Fabamwo, 2012). However, in the wake of this advancement, students from low-income backgrounds often lack access to the necessary technology and internet connectivity, this hinders their educational progress and, consequently, their economic prospects. Linked to the above, Ghavifekr et al. (2023) avers that teacher training and support is essential for effective educational management as education requires ongoing professional development for educators, particularly in digital pedagogy but sadly in Nigeria, funding and logistical challenges often impede comprehensive training programs resulting to the quality of education in Nigeria being compromised. Due to the aforementioned situation, shortage of qualified teachers and inadequate training programs make schools to lack educators in sufficient numbers with the necessary skills and resources to deliver effective instruction, which adversely affects student outcomes and manpower development in need to drive the economy (Ebehikhalu et. al. 2016).

The need for cohesive educational policies that integrate economic recovery strategies poses a significant challenge as fragmented governance structures leads to inconsistencies in educational quality and access (Fabamwo, 2012). Omotayo and Adekunle, (2017) avers that various educational policies have been formulated but there remains a significant gap between policy formulation and implementation. Bureaucratic bottlenecks, lack of political will, and insufficient stakeholder engagement often hinder the successful execution of educational reforms.

Innovative Approach to Educational Management

Despite these challenges discussed above, there are significant prospects for innovative educational management strategies to revitalize the Nigerian educational system that will facilitate economic recovery. One promising approach is the integration of technology in education. Technology education encompasses a broad spectrum of disciplines, including computer science, information technology, and digital literacy. These fields are increasingly essential in a global economy that is progressively leaning towards automation and digitalization. According to the World Economic Forum (2020), as many as 85

billion jobs may be displaced by a shift in labor between humans and machines in 2030, yet 97 billion new roles could emerge that are more adapted to the new division of labor. This highlights the necessity of technology education in preparing a workforce that can fill these emerging roles. Moreover, technology education fosters innovation and entrepreneurship, which are vital for economic revitalization. Research by the Brookings Institution (2021) indicates that regions with higher educational attainment in technology-related fields experience more substantial economic growth and resilience during downturns. By prioritizing technology education, societies can cultivate a skilled workforce capable of driving innovation, thereby creating new industries and revitalizing existing ones.

To achieve the above, partnerships between educational institutions and technology companies must be encouraged. These companies can provide resources and training to schools, thereby bridging the gap of availability of funds to provide quality education by the government as well as the digital divide with emphasis on science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education which can prepare students for high-demand jobs in emerging industries, driving innovation and economic competitiveness (Ramraj & Marimuthu, 2019). Frank & Jekayinfa (2019) opines that this collaborative effort between educational institutions and private sector entities can lead to resource-sharing, curriculum development, and internship opportunities, aligning education with market needs while fostering economic growth. Again, Omotayo and Adekunle, (2017) Proposes Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) engagement in education will enhance resource mobilization and improve service delivery. PPPs facilitate the construction of new schools, provision of learning materials, and training of teachers, thereby alleviating some of the financial burdens on the government. Similarly, Michael, (2014) opines that a focus on skill development aligned with labor market needs is crucial; fostered collaborations of the educational sector with industries will enhance the design of curricula that equip students with relevant skills, thus enhancing employability. Lifelong learning initiatives can also be promoted, encouraging continuous skills development in a rapidly evolving job market.

The need for effective funding mechanisms is paramount to ensure the successful implementation of teacher training programs, infrastructure improvements, and technology integration. Funding not only supports the operational aspects of educational institutions but also plays a crucial role in enhancing the quality of education delivered to students. Often underfunded, teacher training and professional development is integral to improving for schools to produce functional output. According to Darling-Hammond (2017), effective teacher preparation requires substantial investment in both pre-service and in-service training. Funding for professional development can facilitate workshops, mentorship programs, and collaborative learning communities, which are essential for teachers to adapt to evolving pedagogical practice effective classroom management strategies, and curricular demands. An example is the establishment of Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND) in Nigeria. Though functional but more financing is still needed to achieve the goals of education. On infrastructure, the physical infrastructure of educational institutions significantly affects the learning environment. According to the National Center for Education Statistics (2019), many schools in the Nigeria are in dire need of upgrades, with inadequate facilities hindering both teaching and learning processes. Funding for infrastructure provision encompasses not only the building and maintenance of school facilities but also the provision of essential resources such as libraries, laboratories, and recreational areas. Research by the Center for American Progress (2016) indicates that investment in school infrastructure directly correlates with student performance, as well-maintained facilities contribute to a more conducive learning environment.

Furthermore, Edesiri (2021), postulates that, the engagement of stakeholders including parents, businesses, and local communities is essential in the management of education as collaborative efforts can lead to the development of programs that prepare students for specific local job markets. Involving local communities in the management of educational institutions can foster accountability and ensure that schools meet the specific needs of their populations just as Community-based initiatives can also enhance parental involvement in their children's education, leading to improved academic outcomes.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the management of education for economic recovery presents both challenges and opportunities. Addressing funding disparities, digital inequities which is essential for creating an equitable educational landscape, embracing innovative strategies such as technology integration and industry partnerships and also adopting a culture of accountability and community engagement, managing educational will enhance economic revitalization. As the Nigerian societies strive to emerge from these new normal, the commitment to transforming education will be crucial in shaping a resilient and prosperous future.

SUGGESTIONS.

Based on finding this paper suggest the following for educational management to enhance economic recovery

1. To bridge the gap of digital divide among students especially those from poor society economic background and those in rural settlement, school should in addition to the insufficient resources provided by the government seek support from businesses around their locality to support the provision of these equipment and infrastructure in order to produce individuals from the school system that can contribute to their own development and the society at large.
2. Teachers should be develop in their profession by the educational system and also be encouraged to engage in self development that reflect current practices so that the produce from schools are aware of what is required of them in contributing to the development of the economy.
3. Synergy between community, industry and schools should be encouraged since it is education that will be produce the skilled manpower needed by these industries to develop the community.

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